

Ways of strengthening and seismic retrofitting of buildings damaged Izmir due to the reconstruction of Bam earthquake and Kermanshah

S. Sadeghian¹

Abstract— Earthquakes are one of the most important natural hazardous phenomena that occur on the surface of our planet. Controlling the problems caused by the earthquake, in addition to the attention of officials and managers, also requires the help of volunteers and the public. In the present article, with a new and different approach from other articles, the methods of seismic retrofitting and improvement of damaged buildings in Izmir with regard to the reconstruction of Bam and Kermanshah earthquake areas and also, the use of new materials in this regard will be investigated. First, we will compare these earthquakes and their characteristics, and then we will provide information about common systems of construction in Turkey. Finally, practical solutions are proposed to repair and strengthen buildings damaged by earthquakes or buildings that are poorly identified.

Keywords— Earthquakes, retrofitting, tunnel formwork, Concrete

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the different natural risk phenomena that occur on the surface of our planet, destructive earthquakes have the greatest impact on residential areas on the leaves. On average each year, 10,000 people lose their lives in the earthquake. Statistics from UNESCO studies show that the earthquake caused nearly 1 trillion \$ damage between 1926 and 1950. In Central Asia, two cities and 200 villages have been completely destroyed. These statistics provide evidence of the constant human concern about the dangers of earthquake damage. The occurrence of major earthquakes such as Kobe in Japan in 1995 and the earthquake in California in 2003, as well as earthquakes such as the Manjil earthquake in 1980, Ghaenat in 1997 and the Bam earthquake in 2003 in Iran, led everyone to take a different approach to building sturdy structures and building new structures. The widespread and growing need of the society in the construction of durable housing or the improvement of existing buildings requires the investigation of the causes of the demolition of buildings in

the past, which requires special attention of the technical and engineering community and housing officials in the country. Controlling the problems caused by the earthquake, in addition to the attention of officials and managers, also requires the help of volunteers and the public. With the occurrence of large earthquakes in different parts of the world, the importance of dealing with earthquake-resistant structures are felt more (1).

II. THE MAGNITUDE AND SCALE OF EARTHQUAKES

1396 earthquake in Iran - Iraq magnitude 7. 3 Richter evening of Sunday, Persian date Aban 21 1396 near the flock, Kermanshah Province near the border of Iran and Iraq, 32 kilometers southwest of the city of Halabja, Iraq. The epicenter was reported 5 km from Ezgeleh in Kermanshah. The US Geological Survey said the epicenter was 32 kilometers on the outskirts of the Iraqi city of Halabja. The depth of the earthquake was 11 km, which was felt in the entire northwestern region of the country due to its shallow depth and long duration. The quake affected northeastern Turkey and even Kuwait and northern Saudi Arabia. As of December 1, 2017, about 700 aftershocks have shaken Kermanshah province (2).

The Bam earthquake was a 6.6 magnitude earthquake that shook the city of Bam and the surrounding areas in the east of Kerman province for 12 seconds at 5:26 AM on Friday, December 26, 2003. The Bam earthquake with about 50,000 dead was the third deadliest earthquake in the history of Iran after the 272 Ardabil earthquake and the 235 Damghan earthquake. Before the 6.6 magnitude earthquake, there were three mild aftershocks, two of which were felt at around 22:00 and 22:30 the night before, and the third 45 minutes before the main earthquake. However, the intensity of the earthquake, shallow depth, time of occurrence, long duration of the earthquake and the proximity of the epicenter of the city (distance and epicenter of the earthquake in the city of Bam were about four kilometers) caused a lot of damage. Iran earthquake disaster unprecedented in the last century

¹ Junior, Faculty of Engineering, Chalous Branch, Islamic Azad University, Chalous, Iran (e-mail: samet.sadeghian@iauc.ac.ir).

was the incident referred as the deadliest earthquake in history (3).

Izmir is one of the cities of Turkey. Izmir is the third largest city in Turkey after Istanbul and Ankara in terms of size and has a privileged position as a commercial, industrial and port city. Its population was 3,739,353 at the last census in 2008. The city is located on the shores of the Aegean Sea. Izmir's old town is located in what is now Bornova.

Fig. 1 Intensity map of the earthquake

An earthquake measuring 7.0 on the Richter scale struck Izmir on Friday, October 30, 2020 at 1:51 pm, about 14 km northeast of the Greek island of Samos (Fig. 1). Many buildings were damaged or collapsed by the earthquake, the Church of the Blessed Virgin Mary in Karlovasi, Greece was partially destroyed, while in the Turkish city of Izmir, which was severely affected by the earthquake, dozens of buildings were either damaged or completely collapsed. The deadliest earthquake since the earthquake in 2020. The quake was the result of a natural shallow natural fault on the Eurasian plate in the Eastern Aegean Sea, about 250 km north of the nearest main plate boundary, where the African plate moves northward at a speed of approximately 10 mm per year relative to Eurasia (Fig. 2). Therefore, this earthquake is considered as an in-plane earthquake due to its location. Turkey was hit by hundreds of aftershocks following the quake. The magnitude of the earthquake was often reported at 6.6 on the Richter scale due to a mistake made by the Turkish Emergency Management Agency in the Turkish media. At first, Süleyman Soylu Minister of Turkey stated that a minimum of 6 buildings is degraded in Izmir, but later the mayor of the city, the number of collapsed buildings close to 20 buildings. Greek officials in Samos said that although buildings across the island were damaged, the worst situation was in Karlovasi, where the cathedral had partially collapsed.

This is the first time since the 2017 earthquake in the Aegean Sea that deaths have occurred in Greece. Many buildings collapsed in Izmir's Bayraklı and Bornova district (4).

Fig. 2 Map of faults in Turkey

III. COMMON SYSTEM IN TURKISH CONSTRUCTION

The concrete tunnel formwork system is one of the methods used to execute buildings with concrete wall and the roof bearing system (Fig. 3). The name of the tunnel is due to the shape of the metal forms of the walls and ceilings at the same time. In the tunnel system, reinforced concrete walls and ceilings are reinforced, molded and concreted simultaneously. This method, while increasing the speed and quality of execution, significantly improves the performance of the structures and the seismic behavior of the structure in terms of the integrity of the members and their connections. Characteristic features of the modular system, speed, quality and fast conversion are dimensionally different plans for Formatting the system in a way has become a modern format. The result of using this concrete formwork, integrated concrete structures and high-quality concrete surfaces, which leads to the minimum operations required for whitewashing and facade. This formatting method is faster and better than the large panel format in terms of quality and formatting speed.

The system of making concrete structures by the tunnel form method was first invented in France in 1950 And after 40 years in 1990, this system entered Turkey And from the very beginning, it was noticed by mesa company, which is one of the pioneers of the building molding system. After further corrections during work experience, it was finally registered internationally in 2007 by the same company.

Fig. 3 Components of the tunnel formwork system

A. Advantages of tunnel formwork

The advantages of using a tunnel form can be classified into several sub-indicators.

1) Benefits related to technical characteristics

More precise execution and quality control compared to standards

Good earthquake resistance due to the integration of the roof and wall system

Implementing the correct connection of the roof to the wall and not forming an executive seam

High quality concrete surface: Concrete only needs thin gypsum for joinery.

2) Benefits related to economic characteristics

Reduce material waste

Faster return on investment

Long life of the structure due to the integrity of the roof and walls and the execution quality of the building

Reducing construction costs, one of the reasons for which is the high speed of construction

Reducing manpower and consequently reducing costs

The safety of this system in terms of reducing manpower accidents

B. Disadvantages of tunnel form

High initial investment in the preparation of molds

At the beginning of the operation of equipping the workshop, a heavy cost is paid for the supply of machinery and the bulk purchase of materials.

Unnecessary execution of all interior walls in the form of reinforced concrete, which does not change the plan and increases the dead load of the building and the rebar used.

Charge additional costs in case of interruption due to weather conditions

IV. SURVEY OF RETROFITTING

First of all, it should be noted that the highest rate of damage and casualties of the Izmir earthquake relates to the Bornova district, which is the oldest and least developed areas of Izmir, although the technical report of the earthquake has not been published yet. What is certain is that most of the constructions in Turkey and this region are concrete constructions, and these constructions depend on the execution and the quality of the materials. Construction in Turkey is much better than in previous decades and has grown well in improving the quality of construction, but we must not forget that each earthquake has its own characteristics, that is, in no way can the 1999 earthquake in Turkey or the 2011 earthquake in Turkey with an earthquake 2020 compared this country. Even if earthquakes occur in the same area, the depth of the earthquakes may be different and their intensity affects the ground and the amount of damage. Because of this, the magnitude of an earthquake may change.

Fig. 4 A collapsed building in İzmir, Turkey

In Fig. 4, the buildings around the destroyed building are intact. This phenomenon indicates the inappropriate behavior of these buildings with earthquakes, in other words, incompatibility or weakness in design and construction. This is due to poor construction and poor execution of the building or due to a weakness in the building system. That is, a building system may run properly, but be weak in itself. Such a building is not suitable for areas with high seismicity. This

issue needs to be addressed. Another argument is that the building itself may be well constructed and the building system may be suitable, but the building or land in the area or point on which the building is built may not be suitable. For example, the thickness of the sediment should be large and soft. This situation can lead to the phenomenon of earthquake intensification. The soil in one part may be filled, or it may be hand soil, or the soil there may be different from the adjacent soil.

Fig. 5 Subsidence of a building

Or in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, the neighboring building was destroyed, but another survived, which may have been filled with hand soil and loose. Of course, what is more likely is that the destroyed building was not well constructed. Suppose that if the building system of two buildings is similar and one of them is destroyed, that building has not been executed properly and there has been a problem in the execution of the construction and the material of the building materials (Fig. 7). We cannot comment definitively, and accurate commentary requires visiting the site and reviewing it.

Fig. 6 Another collapsed building

Fig. 7 destruction of buildings

V. RETROFITTING

It can be considered as risk reduction techniques and methods in the form of reinforcement methods to achieve stability and resistance of the structure to the lateral load caused by the earthquake (5). Reinforcement regulations have been prepared according to the old studies on earthquake behavior of buildings and comprehensive studies and non-hazardous analyzes of building behavior and their purpose is to improve the seismic capacity of buildings by minimizing their use and observing safety principles and economic issues. For the first time, regulations introduce a new perspective on the reinforcement of non-earthquake-resistant buildings by introducing levels of operation and combining them with earthquake criteria (6).

A. Structural Retrofitting methods

The two main methods for improving the initial condition of the structure in order to deal with the destructive effects of an earthquake are as follows:

- Reducing the need for earthquakes (Demand)
- Increasing the seismic resistance of buildings and structures

1) Reduce the seismic force on the building

Obviously, the seismic force is directly related to its weight, so by reducing the weight of the building, the seismic force on the building can be reduced, which can be done by replacing light walls with heavy walls, using light structural concrete, Styrofoam on the roof, light blocks instead of bricks and proceeded Reduce floors.

2) Add new structural system

In order to add new structural systems for retrofitting, the following methods can be mentioned:

- Add shear wall system in a reinforced concrete building frame
- Use of CBF and EBF centrifugal brace (7)
- Use of intermediates
- Use of viscoelastic damping braces
- Add horizontal curls
- Add vertical coils

- Using new multi-level dampers (8)
- Add load-bearing walls
- Armor using steel mesh and sprayed concrete

It should be noted that the use of any of the above methods alone or in combination with other methods is subject to complete study of the structure and should be considered on a case-by-case basis.

3) *Repair and retrofitting concrete structures*

Rounding with steel, increasing cross-section by concreting and adding reinforcement, epoxy injection, stitching, external prestressing and the use of FRP are some of the methods used by building members depending on the degree of earthquake resistance of the building, possible damage level, type of members and their connections can be repaired and reinforced by them. For example, the FRP matrix consists of a polymer or resin used as a binder for the reinforcing fibers. The use of FRP has been increased because of their high strength to weight ratio, low longitudinal and transverse coefficient of thermal expansion, low sensitivity to fatigue loads and adequate resistant in aggressive environment (9). These methods do not need to be demolished, but the correct connection of old and new sections in reinforced concrete buildings is of special importance when strengthening them. Concrete and finally impregnated with epoxy adhesive with adhesive mortars or cement slurry, the rebars are joined together and then concreting or spraying can be done or new concrete rebars can be made with existing rebars with z and u-shaped patches or by using He made mechanical connections (planting rebar in old concrete or special bolts). Also, recent studies show that in the area which, the strong earthquakes are probable; these structures are vulnerable to seismic failures (10). In this case, this method can be used to create relatively large structural roofs to create temporary or permanent high-speed shelters.

VI. CONCLUSION

Earthquakes are one of the disasters that have always been the focus of human attention due to the casualties and damage they cause. Although earthquakes are relatively mild in some parts of the world and do not disturb the peace of people, science, experience and history have proven that nowhere else on earth. Earthquake-prone areas are not immune to earthquake bites. Because earthquakes behave differently, it is not always possible to predict earthquakes. As some developed countries have been able to tactfully minimize earthquake hazards, we must be prepared and first try to build our buildings and facilities vitally earthquake-resistant, as well as when building stylization. Observe the building and on the other hand, control all seismic points, especially around active faults with the help of precise seismic networks. And earthquakes mild until the danger foreshocks assume and every maneuver earthquake perceived strengths and weaknesses, identify and weaknesses to fix, as well as the recurrence of earthquakes consider and provide scientific issues and implementation plans confidence Let them learn to live next to an earthquake and let them know

that no problem can be solved by panic. Earthquake-damaged or poorly constructed buildings should be repaired and reinforced to withstand subsequent earthquakes until their initial strength is restored or even increased. Renovated buildings must meet ritual requirements. However, repairing or amplifying a building seismically can be very costly. The final decision on whether repairs should be made, and if so, requires a thorough economic review.

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